

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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1990-YILLARDA BUXORODA TURIZMNING RIVOJLANISHI VA MUAMMOLARI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada mustaqillikning dastlabki yillarida Buxoroda turizmning ahvoli, sohadagi muammo va kamchiliklar va ularning sabablari o'rganiladi. 1990-yillarning 2-yarmidagi o'zgarishlar omillari va xalq amaliy san'atining vujudga kelishi bilan bog'liq turizmning rivojlanishiga xizmat qilgan jarayonlar faktlar asosida tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Buxoro, turizm, meros, gid, ekskursiya, kirish turizmi, viza, mehmonxona, "Umrboqiy meros", ziyorat turizmi.

TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN BUKHARA DURING THE 1990S AND ITS PROBLEMS

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Annotations: The article examines the state of tourism in Bukhara in the first years of independence, the problems and shortcomings in the field and their causes. The factors of change in the second half of the 1990s and the processes associated with the establishment of folk arts and crafts, which contributed to the development of tourism, are analyzed on the basis of facts.

Keywords: Bukhara, tourism, heritage, guide, excursion, inbound tourism, visa, hotel, "Lifelong heritage", pilgrimage tourism.

РАЗВИТИЕ И ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУРИЗМА В БУХАРЕ В 1990-Е ГГ.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается состояние туризма в Бухаре в первые годы независимости, проблемы и недостатки в сфере и их причины. На основе фактов анализируются факторы перемен во второй половине 1990-х

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годов и процессы, послужившие развитию туризма, связанные с возникновением народного творчества.

Ключевые слова: Бухара, туризм, наследие, гид, экскурсия, въездной туризм, виза, гостиница, «Наследие всей жизни», паломнический туризм.

After gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan began to develop its economy as a new member of the world economy. In this regard, a number of measures have been developed for the organization and development of tourism, which is expected to be a strategic pillar of the economy of the republic. In particular, in 1992, the Bukhara regional branch of the Uzbektourism National Company was established[1,90-91]. Branches and bureaus of the Bukhara regional branch of the Bureau of Travel and Excursions were also established, including the Gijduvan and Romitan Travel Excursions Bureau. Indicators of domestic and international tourism development in Bukhara are the main parameters of the sector's development. When we analyzed the tourism performance of travel and excursion bureaus in Uzbekistan in April 1992, the Bukhara bureau served 12,200 tourists instead of the planned 5,000, and the plan was fulfilled by 244%. For comparison, the Tashkent Travel Bureau will serve 800 tourists instead of the planned 1,300, or 61.5% of the plan, and the Tashkent Excursion Bureau will serve 2,700 or 54% of the planned 5,000 tourists instead of the planned 5,000. The plan was not implemented. In this regard, instead of serving the plan of 33,600 tourists in Uzbekistan, 27,000 tourists were received, the plan was fulfilled by 80.4%, and the share of Bukhara in the total number of the republic was 45%[2,99]. According to the Bukhara excursion plan, 21,800 people were served instead of 12,400, and the plan was fulfilled by 175.8%. If we compare the number of excursions in the country, Kattakurgan bureau is 100% with 1000 people, Shahrisabz bureau is 211% with 1900 tourists, Chirchik bureau is with 205.7% with 7200 people, Bekabad bureau is with 250 people with 250%, Navoi bureau is with 1800 tourists. In general, only 10 out of 29 tourist excursion bureaus in the country have fulfilled the plan, and the organization that serves the most excursionists is the Bukhara bureau. The fact that the share of Bukhara in the total number of excursion services in Uzbekistan is almost 27% indicates that during this period, the work in this area in the region is well organized.

In the 1990s, the Bukhara Travel and Excursions Bureau, as the main tourist center of Uzbekistan, attracted a large number of tourists[3,99]. Although Bukhara

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region has a great potential for the development of such historical and cultural, pilgrimage tourism, but in this regard, the work was not organized on a large scale. Comparing the organizations of the Bukhara regional branch with the regional branches of other regions of the republic, the regional tour excursion bureau was second only to Tashkent, Fergana, Andijan, Namangan and Samarkand. Due to the inability of the region to use its potential, the establishment of tourist firms and organizations in the districts or territories with tourist resources, as well as the establishment of accommodation facilities was not established. From 1992 to 1995, there were 19 hotels in Uzbekistan, 3 of which were located in Bukhara, with a total number of beds of 1,063. In particular, there were hotels Varakhsha (380 beds), Bukhara (366 beds), Gulistan (317 beds). In 1992-1995, more and more foreign tourists visited the Bukhara Hotel, as it was the only hotel of the highest B level in Bukhara (the highest A level was given only to the Uzbekistan Hotel in Tashkent) and the quality of services was at the level of demand. In particular, during the tourist season, the daily fee at the Bukhara Hotel was \$ 17, and at other times it was \$ 15. In Gulistan and Varakhsha hotels, the figure was 11-9 US dollars[4,113-116]. In 1993, the Bukhara regional branch had 17 organizations related to tourism (tourism, transport, catering)[5,5]. As a result of specialization in Bukhara tourism only in the field of offering historical and cultural heritage sites to tourists, the activities of tourist organizations were limited.

Since Bukhara had the opportunity to organize and further develop the following types of tourism: first, medical tourism (based on Sitorai Mohi Xosa Sanatorium), second, development of ecotourism (based on Jayron Nature Reserve in Karavulbozor district), third, gastronomic tourism (Bukhara Oshi and Gijduvan kebabs), fourthly, tourism of festivals and festivals (Navruz holiday, Nasriddin Afandi comedian), fifthly, pilgrimage tourism (on the example of the Seven Pirs shrines), although the potential for development is very large, but enough attention is paid to this. not given. Even though the locals paid a lot of attention to domestic tourism, unfortunately, the Seven Pirs shrines and the roads leading to them were repaired, but there were no infrastructure facilities for the pilgrims. The reason for this situation in Bukhara tourism in 1991-1994 was, firstly, that the Intourist organization, which had a monopoly on international tourism in the former Soviet Union before the independence, chose Bukhara only for historical and cultural types of tourism. Secondly, even in the period of independence, insufficient measures have

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been taken to identify new tourist destinations, create tourism products or build new infrastructure facilities in the region. In particular, in Romitan, Karakul, Kogan, Karavul Bazar, Shafirkan, Vobkent, Gijduvan districts there are untapped tourist attractions, such as pilgrimage sites, but the lack of tourist infrastructure prevents tourists from coming here. Thirdly, the number of tourist infrastructure facilities in the regions is very limited due to the fact that the activities of private tourism organizations, which provide initiatives and new projects in the field of tourism, are not yet widely established. During the first five years of independence, one of the main problems in the field of tourism in Bukhara was the very small number of licensed travel agencies. In particular, during this period in Uzbekistan there are 65 licensed tourism companies operating in the field of tourism, of which only one, namely, the company "Asia" under the leadership of F. Ochilov was registered in Bukhara. In this regard, compared to other regions of the country, there are 51 travel agencies in Tashkent, 9 in Samarkand, 2 in Khorezm, 1 in Andijan and Fergana, licensed in the field of tourism[6,179-182].

In the first years of independence, there were the following problems with the development of tourism in Bukhara (as in the republic):

- Lack of cooperation with international tourism organizations;
- Lack of publicity for the existing tourist potential of Bukhara in the world;
- Lack of systematic work and direct contacts with foreign partners who organized a trip to Bukhara on the eve of independence to restore previous contracts and increase the number of new ones; 1. Lack of attention to pilgrimage tourism; 2. Insufficient and inadequate range of services provided to foreign tourists and lack of study of international best practices; 3. Lack of tourist staff in the region and the lack of existing staff capacity at the level of international requirements; 4. Instability in the price policy of the hotel and related services in 1991-1993 and the constant rise in prices; 5. Decrease in demand of the local population due to the economic crisis of 1991-1994[7.91].

Due to a number of reasons, such as shortcomings in the management of the tourism industry in Bukhara, the small number of tourist organizations, the lack of systematic promotion of tourism infrastructure and advertising, the country has given its leading role to tourism bureaus in Tashkent and Samarkand region. In this regard, when analyzing the state of domestic tourism in 1995-1999, the total number of services provided by Bukhara tourist organizations was 22,049 people in 1995,

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24,462 people in 1996, 34,231 people in 1997, 28,290 people in 1998. In 1999, it was 33050 people[8.346]. The dynamic growth of 40% during this period was recorded in 1997, the main reason for this positive change was the short-term measures taken in 1997 to celebrate the 2,500th anniversary of the city of Bukhara under the auspices of UNESCO. and the main factor in the increase in the number of visits to Bukhara by local tourists and pilgrims. Bukhara should pay more attention to the development of domestic tourism, as the increase in the number of tourists and pilgrims from all regions of the country will increase the income of the region's economy and stimulate the national economy. In this regard, the use of pilgrimage tourism opportunities is one of the greatest potentials of Bukhara tourism.

The low level of domestic tourism in 1995-1996 compared to outbound tourism is a negative situation for the region's economy. Outbound tourism, which is a part of Bukhara tourism, also underwent development in 1995-1999, and when we analyze outbound tourism, we see that it was more active in the first two years, 1995-1996. In particular, the statistics of outbound tourism by Bukhara tourism organizations shows the following results: 25,813 tourists in 1995, 28,186 tourists in 1996, 17,749 tourists in 1997, 15,777 tourists in 1998, 14,473 tourists in 1999, a total of 101,998 tourists for five years. The tourist was sent out of the region. Of these, 10% were sent to foreign countries, about 2% to CIS countries and 88% to local tourists. This means that the main part of outbound tourism is travel around Uzbekistan, which has a positive economic significance. The main type of tourism in Bukhara is inbound tourism, which is the travel of foreigners to Bukhara, and this type of tourism is a priority due to the fact that it is a factor in the inflow of foreign currency into the region. In 1995, 10079 foreign tourists visited the statistics of inbound tourism, in 1996 - 14952 people, in 1997 - 28211 people, in 1998 - 31565 people, in 1999 - 32515 people[9,346]. In this regard, in 1995-1999, the five-year growth was 222.6%, and the average annual growth was 38%. During this period, a total of 117,322 foreign tourists visited Bukhara through inbound tourism, which was second only to 142,082 domestic tourists in domestic tourism. The dynamic growth of inbound tourism Bukhara tourism has become a driving force in the movement to make positive changes to address the existing shortcomings and problems. The main countries supplying tourists to Bukhara in 1990-2000 were France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Spain, Great Britain, USA, Republic of Korea,

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Switzerland, China, Malaysia, Turkey, Israel, France and Germany[10,334-338]. The main factors of tourist visits to Bukhara are the unique historical, archeological and cultural heritage of Bukhara, the preservation and development of millennial traditions of national art and crafts in the region[11,577]. Influence of such well-known brands as "Samarkand", "Temurlano", "Via della Seta" ("Silk Road"), the price and level of housing services in Bukhara meet average requirements, and most of them are located in the historical center. The high level of friendliness of the local population, the establishment of a representative of the national airline on both sides to create opportunities for tourists[12,152].

Along with tourist organizations, Bukhara handicrafts have a special place in the revival of tourism in Bukhara. In particular, the leading areas of national handicrafts are gold embroidery, jewelry, coppersmithing, carving, ceramics, sewing national costumes, doppi, embroidery, etc. In this regard, masters Jumayev Bakhshillo, Alisher Narzullayev, Shokir Kamolov, Mahfuza Salimova, Usto Samad, Atamuradov Safo, Toshev Davron and others. After gaining independence, many types of handicrafts fell into disrepair, as raw materials for these industries (velvet, gold thread, cardboard) were imported from different regions of the former Soviet Union. Bukhara artisans soon took advantage of the opportunities to solve their problems and set up their own shops and workshops. The first private handicraft workshop in Bukhara was organized by goldsmith Jumayev Bakhshillo. In the past, they rarely participated in exhibitions abroad. In 1994, for the first time in Islamabad, Pakistan, an international festival was held with the participation of artisans from 70 countries. This festival has inspired Uzbek masters to establish cooperation with artisans from Asian countries. Bukhara was the first, and in 1995 the Association of Craftsmen "Lifelong Heritage" was established (including the Charter), which took measures to solve problems in the field, to send master craftsmen to exhibitions and festivals[13,13]. The role of handicrafts in the employment of the population has significantly increased, and in 1997-1998 Bakhshillo Jumayev, acting chairman of the Bukhara regional branch of the Republican Association of Craftsmen, said that 700 artisans were members of the association during this period[14,14]. With the increase in the number of artisans in Bukhara, with the restoration and expansion of ancient handicrafts, non-specific shops of household goods, shops of alcoholic beverages, pharmacies, etc. located in the historical buildings and rooms of the historical center of the city were replaced by craftsmen. Along with the

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establishment of its own workshops and shops, the area has become a prosperous and safe area for night trips for tourists. The production of souvenirs and miniatures has expanded, which has helped to increase the quality and variety of products for tourists.

In conclusion, as a result of the implementation of regulatory and legal measures under the leadership of "Uzbektourism" in the Bukhara regional branch from 1991 to 1999 to overcome the crisis in the field of tourism and excursions, about twenty organizations in the field of tourism, regional bureaus, hotels, campsites, tourist companies have been established. However, the industry and infrastructure facilities did not develop evenly, that is, they were limited to the city of Bukhara. The main shortcoming in this regard is the development of historical and cultural tourism, which is associated only with the city of Bukhara. -cultural events, international forums and conferences, extreme tourism in the desert, travel tourism, rural tourism, international competitions in various sports, the presentation of ecotourism as a tourist product, etc. not set. It is the state and regional programs that neglected the tasks set for the study of some types of tourism, its development as a tourist product and the creation of regulatory, organizational aspects and the creation of its own infrastructure. The process of privatization, which began in 1994-1999, as well as the creative work on the restoration of the Silk Road, historical monuments and shrines of our great ancestors, has received increasing attention. Thanks to the great contribution of Bukhara to world civilization, the celebration of the 2,500th anniversary of the city by UNESCO has become an international event, as a result of which the tourist potential of Bukhara has been widely demonstrated. Unfortunately, international events related to Bukhara have not been continued in various formats in recent years. The benefits and privileges provided by the adoption of the program "Development of foreign and domestic tourism infrastructure in 1996-1997 on the occasion of the 2500th anniversary of the city of Bukhara" have led to positive changes in the tourism industry and related industries in the region. In general, the development of tourism in Bukhara has changed positively compared to the pre-independence period, ie the hotel industry and infrastructure, the number of tourist firms, the number of foreign tourists has increased, and the geography of the countries they visit has slowly expanded. However, Bukhara tourism, like the country's tourism industry, lagged far behind the level of development of world tourism. For many years, shortcomings and problems in the system have negatively

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affected the development of the industry, preventing the creation of new tourism products, the rapid expansion of tourist audiences and geography, the introduction of new services and the strategic position of tourism in the economy.

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7. MA RUz, fund M-141, list 1, case 42, sheet 91.
8. Bukhara regional state archive (BVDA), fund M-1503, list 1, case 27, page 346.
9. BVDA, Fund M-1503, List 1, Case 27, Page 346.
10. BVDA, fund M-1503, list 1, case 27, pages 334-338.
11. To date, 829 objects of material cultural heritage are under state protection in Bukhara region. Of these, 287 are archeological monuments, 507 are architectural objects, 17 are monumental art and 18 are attractions and have been preserved in their original condition.https://buxoro.uz/full_news.php?dt=news&id=577
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